

Constraining Slab-Edge Driven Mantle Flow in the Cascadia Subduction Zone

SAMANTHA KOLLER, Pikes Peak State College, Colorado College

Twin Mentor 1: Margarete Jadamec, University at Buffalo

Twin Mentor 2: Maureen Long, Yale University

ABSTRACT

Geophysical observations indicate modern slabs are discontinuous with lateral slab edges, yet the three-dimensional dynamics of slab edge driven mantle flow is less understood. To address this, we compiled over a decade of shear wave splitting (SWS) measurements from the Cascadia Subduction Zone to constrain high-resolution, 3D geodynamic models. The data were partitioned into four domains: the southern Juan de Fuca slab edge region, central Cascadia subduction zone, northern Juan de Fuca slab edge region, and offshore region where the plate has not yet been subducted. In the southern slab edge region, fast directions south of the slab edge change from SE-NW to E-W to NE-SW with depth, with mirrored directions north of the southern slab edge forming a circular pattern, consistent with previous observations. In the central subduction zone, fast azimuths are approximately E-W and trench-perpendicular, as previously shown. In the northern slab edge region, fast directions are more scattered (E-W to NE-SW), suggesting an arcuate shape that may represent a larger circular pattern like the southern edge. Fast directions within the central Juan de Fuca plate are generally NE. In the next phase of this work, these seismic observations will be compared to output from new three-dimensional, high-resolution geodynamic models of Cascadia that incorporate natural slab geometry. This integration will help illuminate slab-driven mantle flow in natural subduction systems and its role in anomalous volcanism at the northern and southern slab edges in Cascadia, with broader implications for slab edges elsewhere in the Pacific Ring of Fire.

INTRODUCTION

The Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) spans from northern California, United States, through the Pacific northwest, and up to British Columbia, Canada (Currie et al. 2004; Long, 2016). CSZ consists of the Juan de Fuca plate, Gorda, and Explorer plates subducting below the North American plate at a rate of ~40 mm/year (4.0-4.5cm/year) (figure 1) (Currie et al. 2004; Long, 2016). The CSZ region has a volcanic ridge at the divergent boundary between the Pacific plate and the Juan de Fuca plate, a trench running mostly parallel to the coastline, and an inboard volcanic arc parallel to the trench (Liu et al., 2014; Long, 2016). The subduction of the Juan de Fuca plate drives mantle flow in the asthenosphere under and around the slab (Currie et al., 2004; Eakin et al., 2010; Long, 2016). It is characterized as a noncontinuous, young, hot oceanic plate as compared to other subducting plates globally (Long, 2016). One more notable feature of Cascadia is anomalous volcanism observed in the High Lava Plains of Oregon (Long et al., 2009; Long, 2016) and also adjacent to both the northern and southern lateral slab edges of Cascadia.

As a slab subducts beneath the overriding plate, mantle becomes displaced resulting in the mantle flowing in relation to subduction (Jadamec, 2016). CSZ is noncontinuous and has lateral slab edges. These lateral edges result in three-dimensional mantle flow that is not widely understood. Based on SWS measurements and interpretations, mantle flow in the region is generally agreeable with absolute plate motion except at the slab edges, where a circular flow pattern appears around the slab edge, referred to as toroidal flow (Eakin et al., 2010; Jadamec, 2016; Long, 2016). Understanding the relationship between subduction and mantle flow, especially around slab edges, has implications for a greater understanding of volcanism in the vicinity of the Cascadia subduction zone and other subduction zones around the Pacific Ring of Fire (Long and Becker, 2010; Long, 2016; Jadamec, 2016; Jadamec et al., 2018; Jadamec et al., 2024).

In this study, we collected shear wave splitting measurements from a decade of studies across Cascadia with the purpose of compiling data for constraining 3D geodynamic models of the region. We isolated the data into distinct regions: the southern Juan de Fuca slab edge region, the central Cascadia subduction zone, the northern Juan de Fuca slab edge region, and the offshore region where the Juan de Fuca plate has not yet been subducted. The data were processed using MATLAB scripts, with the intention of being used for comparison with the geodynamic models in the future.

Figure 1. Tectonic setting for the Cascadia Subduction zone. Red triangles display the location of volcanoes in the region. The thick black arrows show absolute plate motion along with their velocities. The thin black arrows are showing notable features. States are in black letters with their abbreviations. The Purple arrow is the relative convergence between the Juan de Fuca plate and the North American plate. The blue arrow shows the relative motion of the Juan de Fuca trench (reprinted from Long, 2016).

BACKGROUND

Shear wave splitting (SWS) is a seismologic phenomenon in which shear waves “split” into two polarized shear waves when passing through a material that has different properties or behaviors when measured in different directions, also known as anisotropic materials (Long and Becker, 2010). When an earthquake occurs, there are two distinct waves that travel, primary waves (p-waves) and shear waves (s-waves) (Long and Becker, 2010). S-waves arrive secondary to p-waves and are responsible for the shaky motions of the ground we associate with strong earthquakes (Long and Becker, 2010). What makes these waves so special from a seismological standpoint is their ability to polarize when passing through anisotropic mediums (Long and Becker, 2010). This is specifically related to the passage of s-waves through olivine crystals (Long and Becker, 2010; Long, 2016). Olivine is the most abundant mineral in the upper mantle and is widely understood to develop a lattice preferred orientation within the olivine crystal structure when subject to deformation, or strain (Long and Becker, 2010; Long 2016). When s-waves pass through these olivine crystals, they can split into two polarized shear waves, with one of these polarized waves travelling faster than the other (Long and Becker, 2010; Long, 2016). The difference in velocity between the two waves is measured as the delay time and can be an indication of the thickness of the anisotropic layer and/or the strength of the anisotropic layer (Long,

2016). These waves also change their direction in accordance with the preferred lattice orientation of the olivine crystals (Long, 2016), giving us a reasonable depiction of mantle flow at the location of the measurement (Long, 2016). Therefore, SWS measurements are important because they give a reasonable assessment of deformation due to mantle flow (Long and Becker, 2010) and may indicate the thickness of the anisotropic layer in each region (Long, 2016).

METHODS

Data used in this study were all gathered from five studies of the Cascadia subduction zone and nationwide studies of SWS (Table 1). The data compiled came from studies in 2009 (Long et al., 2009), 2010 (Eakin et al., 2010), 2014 (Liu et al., 2014), and 2015 (Bodmer et al., 2015 and Martin-Short et al., 2015). All SWS measurements focused specifically on SKS and SKKS waves from earthquakes at distances anywhere from 85-180 degrees depending on the study. Most of the studies used are specific to the Cascadia subduction zone with the exception of Liu et al. (2014). More details for the shear wave splitting studies used can be found in the data synthesis in Table 1. In addition, slab surface and contour plots were made to visualize 3D slab geometry using the Slab2 (Hayes et al., 2018) surface geometry data.

The data were processed using MATLAB scripts. The 3D slab projection was made in MATLAB using the scatter function and superimposing the contours using meshgrid. Each SWS plot was made first by creating a base map and then plotting the SWS measurements and then the station locations. A scale bar is added along with a title. Plots are then named based on the paper the data set originated from.

Author (Year)	Purpose of the Study	Methods	Assumptions/Findings
Long et al., 2009	Evaluate SWS data in the High Lava Plains of eastern Oregon. Characterize pattern of active mantle flow in the region. Distinguish between lithospheric and asthenospheric contributions to anisotropy.	Splitting measurements made with SplitLab software. Events are 5.8 magnitude at epicenters between 88 deg and 130 deg. Magnitude 5.8 or greater. Bandpass filtered between 0.1 and 0.01 Hz, with some manual adjustment of filters for signal clarity.	Found 6-8% anisotropy for a 150 km thick asthenosphere based on their measured delay times.
Eakin et al., (2010)	To better understand seismic anisotropy between the CSZ and Mendocino triple junction (where the Pacific, North American and Juan De Fuca plates meet).	Analysis done with SplitLab package. Bandpass filter of 0.03 to 0.3 Hz. Fast direction and delay times determined using a grid search using both the minimum energy of Silver and Chan (1988, 1991) and rotation correction of Bowmann and Ando (1987).	Focus on areas with denser measurements, averaged from 100 km to only 200-300 km depth. Assume 4% anisotropy and S-wave velocity of 4.6 km/s when determining layer thickness.
Liu et al., 2014	Presents SWS database for the western and central United States. For our purposes, we will specifically focus on observations of Cascadia.	Utilizes the minimization energy method from Silver and Chan (1991). Events of magnitudes 5.5 with focal depth >100 km. Epicentral distance ranges are 84 deg-180 deg for SKKS and SKS. Band-pass filtered from 0.04-0.5 Hz.	No major assumptions made in interpretation (focus is on presenting splitting database).

Bodmer et al., 2015	Evaluate SKS shear wave splitting in offshore region using ocean bottom seismometer (OBS) data to determine mantle flow patterns in Cascadia.	Horizontal orientation determined by Sumy et al. (2015), with medium uncertainty in channel orientation of 9 deg at the 1 confidence level. Silver and Chan (1991) analysis method. Analyze SKS phase of teleseismic events M 6 at distance 90 to 130 deg.	Assuming observed fast directions are subparallel to direction of maximum shear. 4% mantle anisotropy, split time ~1 s, and require a ~100 km thick anisotropic layer.
Martin-Short et al., 2015	Analyze seismic anisotropy as expressed in SKS splitting to determine the asthenospheric mantle flow from the Juan De Fuca mid-ocean ridge to Cascadia subduction zone. Use OBS data.	Utilize SplitLab and SHEBA to measure splitting SKS and SKKS waves. Magnitude 6 distances of 85-130 deg. Bandpass filter of 0.03-0.1 Hz. Events with signal-to-noise greater than 4.0 were used to stack, and frequencies below 0.14 Hz omitted to avoid signal energy reduction.	Alignment of fast directions with Juan de Fuca Plate motion; Gorda Plate fast directions align with nearby Pacific Plate motion.

Table 1. Table synthesizing the data used in this study. The author, year of publication, purpose of the study, methods used, and assumptions made is included in the table to offer perspective into how the original data sets were collected and what assumptions will be consistent within the data.

RESULTS

Figure 2A shows the slab contours projected onto a geographic map of the subduction zone. Figure 2B shows a 3D image of the slab that has been subducted. The slab dips at a steep angle and fragments with depth. In addition, the slab dips at a slight angle with the deepest descent near 40 degrees latitude. The slab is also not perfectly flat, and has areas that protrude out more than others, such as the feature around the 50 degrees mark. The contours help to identify these features.

Figure 2. Cascadia slab with contours plotted in (a) map view and (b) three-dimensional perspective using MATLAB. The black lines (blue in a) indicate the slab contours at an interval of 20 km. The color scale indicates the depth of the slab in km. Slab data from Hayes et al. (2018).

Figure 3 shows the average splitting time and fast directions for Cascadia. Fast direction changes greatly with Latitude (Figure 3). Fast directions within the central Juan de Fuca plate are generally NE (Figure 3a-3b). In the northern slab edge region, the fast directions are more scattered, ranging from E-W to NE-SW (Figure 3b-3c and Figure 4b), suggesting an arcuate shape that may be part of a larger circular pattern similar to that at the southern slab edge. In the southern slab edge region, fast directions south of the slab edge change from SE-NW and E-W to E-W to NE-SW in the down-dip direction with mirrored directions on the north side of the southern slab edge resulting in an overall circular pattern (Figure 3c and 4b). In the central subduction zone, fast azimuths are approximately E-W and in the trench-perpendicular direction (Figure 3d). The delay times overall average ~ 1 s with some areas averaging near 1.5s (Figure 3). The highest delay times are located in the High Lava Plains where there is a significantly higher number of measurements and significantly longer delay times (Figure 3d).

Figure 3: SWS data plotted in MATLAB for the (a) Bodmer et al. data set (Bodmer et al., 2015), (b) Martin-Short et al. data set (Martin-Short et al., 2015), (c) Eakin et al. data set (Eakin et al., 2010), and (d) the High Lava Plains data set (Long et al., 2009).

DISCUSSION

The location of the slab edges, the fast direction of the SWS measurements, and the average delay times suggest mantle flow around the slab edges in Cascadia presents as counterclockwise toroidal flow in the south and clockwise toroidal flow in the north (Figures 3 and 4). Figure 4b displays in greater detail the scale of the circular SKS pattern around the southern slab edge in Cascadia, as shown in previous work (Liu et al., 2014; Long, 2016), and displays where volcanoes related to slab edge upwelling may be located. Future high-resolution 3D geodynamic models will examine the slab-driven flow in Cascadia (Kolke, MS thesis proposal, 2025) and test for upwelling associated with the toroidal flow at the slab edges in Cascadia, as suggested by previous models of both toroidal flow and slab-edge upwelling at the eastern slab edge in the Alaska subduction zone (Jadamec et al., 2024). By using the SWS plots compiled in this study as constraints, future 3D geodynamic models will better understand the flow of the mantle in Cascadia, which may be translated to understanding slab-edge processes at other subduction zone systems globally.

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